

Review

Viral Marketing Concept and Viral Marketing Development on Consumer Buying Approach

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Abstract

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Due to the technological developments, especially in the marketing fields, this has led to the emergence of the so-called viral marketing. Therefore, most marketers and their commercial production, and service firms are taking action to develop their marketing approaches, which are used by firms to increase their competitive advantages through enhancing brand awareness, achieving a high interaction rate by mouse clicking and increasing sales volume, to maximizing their revenues. On the other hand, in order to achieve the firm's mission and vision. This study focuses on the concept of viral marketing, the purpose and importance of viral marketing, viral marketing strategies.

Keywords: Viral Marketing, Buying approach, word of mouse

INTRODUCTION

Marketing science is an ancient science. This is because marketing has been and still is one of the vital economic activities that play an essential and active role towards the growth and continuity of the manufacturing organizations, service organizations, and marketing organizations in the market. Owing to the development in the external environment and technological development that has greatly affected the development of consumer behavior, through openness to and being affected by the civilizations of others, the process the marketing concept evolution has passed from various stages to finally reach the modern marketing concept adopted by organizations at the present time, for the purpose of meeting the consumers' needs and desires through providing products that meet these needs and desires (Akaileh, 2015). However, the evolution of the marketing concept did not stop at the modern concept. Rather, many other marketing-related concepts have emerged during this stage such as green marketing, social marketing, guerrilla marketing, electronic marketing and viral marketing, which reflects the interest of marketers in developing marketing activities in proportion to the development taking place in the marketing environment and the consumers' needs and desires, through

encouraging them to try the products offered in the market, and achieving the organization' objectives, taking into consideration the preservation of the environment and society. In this regard, the evolution of the marketing concept was accompanied by a great development in the means of communication and information, which encouraged marketing operators to adopt it in order to reach out to the targeted markets (Solomon, 2012), (Akaileh, 2015).

The concept of viral marketing is one of the modern concepts that have emerged recently. Viral marketing relies on the use of the Internet and social networks to send marketing e-mails, and to encourage recipients of e-mails to voluntarily forward them to family, friends, and people close to them, which consequently lead to generating a wide and rapid spread of emails sent from organizations (Akaileh, 2015).

The emergence of the Internet and the services it is providing made a great development in marketing activities, and enabled organizations to further expand their sales from targeting the local market only to targeting foreign markets. This was not limited to large organizations only, but it included small businesses with limited resources as well; thus, small business also

managed to appear in foreign markets through promoting their products and sell them through Internet, where Hotmail is one of the successful experiences that used viral marketing in sending and spreading its e-mails, through encouraging its users to forward them to friends and family, which encouraged organizations to urge Internet users to voluntarily forward their emails to other users, and monitor the extent of viral marketing impact on their products sales volume and the popularity, and on the dissemination of its messages through the network, in addition to monitoring the extent to which Internet users follow up and forward these messages, which has contributed significantly to reducing the time, effort, and costs for organizations to reach out to the target markets (Youssef, (2009).

As the concept of viral marketing is one of the modern concepts in the marketing science, it is necessary for manufacturing organizations, service organizations, and marketing organizations to study the impact of viral marketing activities on encouraging customers to try the products, its impact on the individuals' buying behavior, its impact on the reputation and fame of organizations, its impact on achieving marketing goals such as sales increase, gaining new customers, and increasing product and brand awareness through having these customers create and send viral emails which will appeal to social media users, and urge them to forward them to other users.

Literature Review

Service organizations strives to reach out to the target markets and gain new customers by means of using of the Internet and through disseminating of their e-mails, in order to achieve a fast-paced spread capacity, at the lowest costs, in addition to working on meeting the customers' needs and desires, building bridges of trust with them, as well as adopting modern technologies, keeping pace with development, and adopting means of communication that enable reaching the target markets through the Internet and social networking sites. Viral marketing is one of the marketing concepts that plays an effective role through word-of-mouth, encouraging individuals to spread the organization's emails to others, and urging them to forward them to family and friends voluntarily, which will generate a rapid growth in the number of users of e-mails posted by these organizations. Thus, all these data and guiding practices have led to attracting and motivating many competent authors and researchers to investigate this topic.

Youssef, (2009) focused on measuring the impact of the application of viral marketing on buying decision; the study showed that that the concept of viral marketing appeared first based on it's on the spoken words through the Internet and contacting individuals' websites, in order to implement marketing activities. In addition, the study

investigated whether this concept and its application have a significant impact on behavior and buying decision. The most important findings of the study are that there is relationship and an impact of viral marketing on the consumer buying decision, and that there is a relationship between the concept of viral marketing, and the spread of advertising messages through websites; also, it was found that the information sent via are important, credible, and reliable, which consequently lead to forming a positive image about the sending organization.

According to what was stated in Sadiq (2008), business organizations adopt this concept to promote their services through social networking websites to achieve their goals. The study recommended that commercial organizations and businesses must apply viral marketing and all its tools to their departments if they want to achieve success in terms of customer satisfaction on the one hand, and achieve profits on the other hand. The study, Abu Fara, (2008) showed the strategies of this viral marketing and the consequent risks facing the contemporary marketing, and that many international companies have used the concept of viral marketing and viral campaigns to promote their services and products. Also, the study stated some of the most used practices through communication through websites including the importance of showing care for the current customers, maintain them, and attract new customers to become a defense attorney for these companies that have adopted this concept.

The study of AminaTalatet.al(2013), focused on the extent to which Internet users accept the social trading that is implemented through social media and social networking via Internet. Also, the study explored how these practices support social interaction and activities that help the network user in Pakistan to buy through the Internet, in addition to studying the relationship between risks and social networks, emotional impact, advertising, and word-of-mouth. The findings of this study indicate that Internet users in Pakistan welcome commerce through social trading even for those who have no previous experience in online commerce.

In the same context (Singh, (2012) revealed that viral marketing gained rapid spread and recognition through motivating employees, which resulted in an increase in dealing among customers, leading in turn to sales increase, building brand awareness, and covering markets, as viral marketing has become very effective and low-cost. The requirements of customer management include that is should be effective and to stand in a position that enables controlling everyone, and that the organizations seeking to use it must be careful in dealing, make plans for that, and therefore it is considered part of the overall marketing strategy. Thus, the possibility of raising the power of viral marketing is enabled, lighting up the way for researchers and organizations.

In the same context, the study of Danias, (2010)

aimed to investigate increase the importance of social media and social marketing via the Internet, and measure the improvement of investment and exploitation of social media and viral marketing communications, and it is noted that the role of marketing has changed, and these means promote this change. The study noted that the role of marketing has changed, and that these means investigated in the study promote this change, which creates both a challenge and opportunities at the same time for marketing. Also, the study stressed the importance of advertising in a more effective way, and emphasized that the spread of information among individuals and its dissemination is very fast through the word-of-mouth, and that viral marketing has a major role in reducing promotion costs through social media. Peterson, (2001) showed the extent of the impact that takes place when Internet is used in building marketing channels, and that customers and customers are looking for goods and services on the websites to which producers and sellers those goods and services subscribe. Consequently, this plays a major role in the emergence of competition and the competitive advantage and in the processes of motivating customers to order such goods and services. The study found that Internet marketing plays a pivotal role in pricing, as the seller offers his goods and services, and the customer receives sufficient information about this offered good or service.

Problem statement:

In light of the many modern terms accompanying the technological development and the communications and information revolution, which greatly affected all commercial, production, and service sectors, which seek to benefit from these concepts through using them in order to attract customers, increase their market share, and enhance the competitive position in the market, and despite the role that viral marketing plays in re-disseminating information and e-mails about organizations, their products and services, urging and encouraging recipients of e- to forward them to others, the researcher still finds that there is some ambiguity in the concept of viral marketing concept, and the role it plays in influencing the organizations' encouragement and retention of the current clients as well as attracting potential new clients.

Purpose of the study

Marketers find that the adoption of viral marketing has enabled them to encourage large numbers of customers to take advantage of their services and products, which has led to increased sales and increased brand awareness at low costs. The viral marketing strategy is based on encouraging customers to communicate with

others and forward the organization's emails to them, which gives the organization rapid growth opportunities through word-of-mouth marketing and through the fast-paced spread of messages to thousands or even millions of individuals.

Acquiring the best knowledge of viral marketing is through the context of the historical development of the marketing concept, since the early beginning of barter process between individuals and groups, to the industrial revolution, which played the central role in increasing the quantity and diversity of production; where the barter and sale were done through word-of-mouth to turn later into broad marketing, moving from inside the factory to outside, emphasizing the study of the needs and desires of customers, and working to meet them through adopting the modern concept of marketing to reach the social concept of marketing, green marketing. In this regard, as the case with all workers in the scientific and human fields who seek to benefit from technological development, the communications and information revolution, and the emergence of the Internet, marketers on their part also worked on this, which contributed to the emergence of electronic marketing and viral marketing. Therefore, the researcher devoted this part to reviewing the marketing concept in the pre-Internet era and the pots-Internet era.

Marketing concept in the pre-Internet era

Marketing operations have been engendered since the emergence of barter of trade exchange since ancient times. There has been a great development in marketing thought and the marketing concept as a result of technological development, development in the surrounding environment, and the evolution of the needs and desires of consumers; and these developments have affected marketing activities (Akaileh, 2015). Distinguishing products and services has become of great importance, which prompted marketers to know the needs and desires of consumers and to know their reactions to these products. This trend has contributed to identifying and adopting the elements of the marketing mix, and the orientation towards relationship marketing in the eighties, and the adoption of modern means of communication (Sadiq, 2012).

Marketing concept in the post-Internet era

The world has witnessed a huge revolution in communications and information technology that contributed to the emergence of the Internet, which brought about many changes and transitions in the field of business dealings, and contributed to creating many benefits, whether for large-scale or small-scale organizations, and even for individuals. This is because

internet removed barriers facing the process of communication and commercial dealings on the international market level, enabled the speed in the transmission and spread of information, the convergence of distances, reducing costs, and many other benefits that helped the spread of marketing via the Internet, and enabled the reaching out of information related to the product / service and its promotion electronically. Thus, this constitutes a challenge facing organizations, forcing them to think about advancing marketing to nontraditional levels which resulted in the appearance of contemporary concepts of marketing, such as green marketing, viral marketing, social marketing, social responsibility and others. And this has made the Internet an electronic market today, and its use has increased by organizations of all kinds. Thus, the Internet has provided many organizations and companies with electronic dealing at the lowest costs.

Online marketing or e-marketing in general can be an attempt to enhance both sales and communications, contact details, product sales, product and brand promotion, after-sales options, and customer reactions to products and information...etc. Mainly, it can be stated that organizations target the following through electronic marketing (Robinson et al, 2007):

- Enhancing brand awareness, as the advertising message focuses on it;
- Achieving a high interaction rate by clicking on the ad banner;
- Increasing sales volume;
- Achieving widespread.

Concept of viral marketing

Individuals in general have a tendency to communicate with others, transfer information and ideas to them, and influence their decisions and attract them. Thus, marketers have sought to take advantage of this feature through viral marketing. Some researchers in this regard indicate that the spread and transmission of stories from generation to generation and the transmission of traditions, religions, knowledge, and culture through the transmission of speech and its viral spread expresses the nature of human beings in transmitting stories and news and spreading it to those around them. Based on this feature that characterizes individuals and their desire to transmit news, the organizations have worked on making use of this feature through traditional marketing and viral marketing.

The classic example of viral marketing is Hotmail.com, one of the first free e-mail services on the Internet. The strategy which Hotmail adopted relies on knowing the addresses and free e-mail services of the target audience, where a simple sign is placed at the bottom of each message indicating it is sent for free at "http://www.hotmail.com", and that people who have their

own e-mail to connect with their friends, and to whom emails are sent can subscribe for free through their e-mail, thus influencing the buying decision to increase sales volume and brand awareness (Stephen, 2001).

Viral marketing is termed so as it denotes the spread of advertisements or news and its transmission among people, such as a virus that infects a person, and then speeds to others quickly. Here, the virus here means an electronic advertising message in the form of text, image, or video, that can be shared through social media such as Facebook, Twitter, and chat applications and means owned by some websites have to share the opinion of customers on the product and the speed it between people with ease, which makes the post that a company or organization published reaches a very large number as fast as possible at the lowest cost, and this is what is termed a 'viral message'. This is because the subscriber will see the posts of his friends that they share on his page, and he is forced to see them just like a virus that is transmitted without one's control, as well as using videos on YouTube channels, and sharing them to many friends on the page, and thus achieving the greatest results from the viral campaign (Sadiq, 2008).

Here it should be pointed out how to start a viral marketing campaign:

First: Write the idea that you want to promote, and consider the service or product to be marketed through a picture, text, or video.

Second: Create a website so that your customers and clients can direct their friends and acquaintances to it.

Third: Put the feature of follow up on updates by placing the e-mail address in a clear place for everyone or at the end of each message that is sent.

There are many definition of viral marketing; however, no unified definition of this concept has been reached.

Brewer, (2001) sees that viral marketing is a strategy of encouraging individuals to transmit or market a message to others, and that is creates the possibility of growth based on the increasing rate of exposure to the impact of the message, and that this exposure plays an active role in spreading it and its impact on others, because receiving a message or receiving an idea from a trustworthy person may have a greater impact than receiving the message from the organization directly; for that, organizations work to motivate Internet users and their customers to forward and send the message to others through the material and moral motivation that it gives them.

For Sandeep, (2000), he defined viral marketing as a method that represents a new way to increase market penetration and build brand awareness through the use of the Internet.

Howell & Smith, (2003) see hat viral marketing as a method that works to push individuals to forward messages sent to them, provided that its programs are exceptional and able to attract attention and receive the

message, and that it is characterized by its low costs due to its reliance on free websites, which encourages individuals to forward the messages.

Also, Silverman (2007) Sauer, (2004) have defined viral marketing as a marketing phenomenon that facilitates and encourages individuals who receive advertising messages to voluntarily forward them to others; and it represents a marketing technique that uses social networks, and encourages individuals to disseminate it through adopting the word being transmitted. For Modzele Wski (2000), he sees that viral marketing differs from the spoken word marketing, because viral marketing uses it in spreading messages, which is broader and more comprehensive than spoken word marketing, as the value and viral strength of the message that reaches the first user/customer is directly related to the numbers of users/customers whom this first user can succeed in attracting.

Besides these definitions, Riemer et al. (2002), Zien, (2000) on their part is categorized viral marketing into two main categories: active viral marketing, which implies the speed of messages spread, and the influence on the response of the Internet users, and the inactive viral marketing, which spreads slower than the active viral marketing, as it penetrates slowly, and serves to reinforce the users' attitudes toward product messaging.

According to the foregoing, we find that viral marketing is a marketing technique that centers all its focus and reliance on making use of the efforts of social networking sites users, chats, and mobile phones users, in a way that encourages them to spread electronic advertising messages to others, to encourage them in turn to buy the advertised products through offering them discounts in return for spreading their advertising messages.

The evolution of viral marketing

The first to use this term recently is the media writer (Doglas, 1994) in her book *Media Viral*, as she derived formulating this concept based on the speed of information transmission and advertising among Internet users, especially social media websites, in order to promote products, advertisements, and reach out to the largest number of customers and convince them to forward the message to family and friends, in return for an incentive or reward.

In 1996, this term was used by Jeffrey F. at Harvard Business School in his article "The Virus of Marketing." And in 1997 Steve Jurvetson described the Hotmail experience, (Outlook), then in 2003, he invented the term "Alpha user", which indicates that it has become possible to identify the active members of any viral campaign, and that they may be targeted for advertising purposes

through mobile networks. Also, recently in 2013, a conference was held in Las Vegas to identify and define similar trends in viral marketing methods by viral media. As an idea, it was implemented by Steve Jurvetson and Tim Draper at Microsoft Hotmail, which was a free e-mail service, where e-mails in their reality represented an advertisement and thus spread the messages they received to their friends, colleagues, and relatives. However, it was used by organizations in a simple and limited range at first, then started to increase gradually, to reach its climax especially with the development of electronic business and the development of Internet networks.

The beginning of the emergence of viral marketing was as an approach to advertising; and it was based on the basis that ideas spread like viruses, which encouraged marketers to adopt it (Burman, 2014).

This type of marketing strategy was termed with different names, including viral marketing, viral advertising or marketing buzz. Viral marketing is a process similar to the spread of viruses or computer viruses that are transmitted and delivered by word-of-mouth through chat and forwarding messages or through mobile phones (Howard, 2005). In viral marketing, organizations use videos, interactive games, adventure games, books and software, photos, text messages, emails, web pages, and mobile messages.

Chevalier and Mayzlin, (2006) pointed out that the Hotmail user base has grown very rapidly, exceeding the growth rate of any media outlet throughout history. Individuals communicate with each other and through this communication they transmit information, as individuals, by nature, transmit the word to twelve people from family and friends. If their experiences are good, they will pass it on to them and their impact will be effective, but when their experiences are not good, they will have a negative impact on the messages and products advertised, which they will transfer as well to friends and family (Youssef, 2009).

Sadiq (2008) points out that Sony company in Italy established an open website for internet users, and this company was able, and in a short period of seven weeks devoted to promoting the MP3/4 player Sony Walkman, to attract more than 130000 visitors.

Viral marketing relies on sending messages in the form of videos, effective games, advertising games, e-books, pictures, articles, and writings, and advertising messages via the Internet or social networks, and urging the recipients to voluntarily forward them to others. Viral marketing implies any strategy that encourages individuals and organizations, and motivate them to pass marketing messages to others. In viral marketing, the marketing strategies focus on the speed of spread through relying on electronic applications, to spread these messages to thousands or even millions, via the Internet just like the way a virus is spread.

Benefits of applying viral marketing

Applying viral marketing in any organization or company helps achieve many benefits, especially the speed of spread among Internet traders to promote their products and services, and this creates an increase in the number of those wishing to view and share such posts. In this point, it is necessary to refer to the benefits achieved through applying this viral marketing technology in the business organizations market (Sadiq, 2008):

- Increasing sales;
- Building electronic mailing list;
- Generating targeted signals.

Among the benefits of this technology when applied by banks on the Internet:

- It works in the midst of information, and deals with the language of numbers which is characterized by its accuracy;
- Low cost or distribution/or no cost at all;
- Easier and faster for the recipient;
- Permanent and continuous archive, and the ability to link and direct contact;
- Cross usage (connecting to more than one source at the same time).

The importance of viral marketing

The importance of viral marketing manifests in:

- Spreading advertising messages and motivating individuals to voluntarily forward them to others.
- Assisting in the distribution of products (goods or services), through publishing them on social networking websites to promote them through these networks.
- Obtaining high sales volumes and promoting them through electronic networks, as Gladwell, (2005) indicated that (20-40%) of the sales of Amazon company on its website (Amazon.com) are achieved through the framework of the main chain of the main categories offered on the Internet. this site;
- Reducing marketing costs;
- Building brand loyalty.

Craig (2014) sees that viral marketing plays an important role in rapid brand awareness. Viral promotional campaigns should generate quick and easy reactions in message recipients and push them to spread the word to others. Companies also seek to attract the experienced social media users to design advertising messages through making new product features the focal point of viral marketing efforts, and launch the message and asks social networking and experienced users to express their opinion, put forward their ideas, and comment on the product and the message.

The importance of viral marketing lies also in marketing niche products with limited market segments, which leads to substantial contributions in the website's total sales volume (Anderson, 2006), as the best findings

of studies include the use of viral marketing strategies for such market segments.

Objectives of viral marketing

Considering the role that viral marketing plays in attracting customers during a limited period of time at the lowest costs, the most important goals that viral marketing seeks to achieve include the following Fritz, (2004):

1. Reaching out to the largest possible number of customers and retaining existing customers or potential customers, through the so-called honest and trusted word-of-mouth enhanced by the quality of the product and the benefits they customers gain from the product; and as all may know, that the cost of gaining one new customer is more six times than the cost of retaining the current customer.
2. Maximizing revenues and profits for sales of goods and services through viral marketing (Randall 1997). This is because the impact of capabilities of viral marketing tools on the increase in the amount of sales and product revenues for e-business organizations exceed the capabilities of traditional advertising tools in organizations, in addition to the fact that products information is for free and the costs of the distribution process through websites and social networks is much less than distribution through traditional distribution points, and thus organizations can maximize their profits and revenues.

The website of Hotmail company managed to double its user database in less than three years, to reach more than 40 million subscribers; afterwards, the company sold the website to Microsoft it for \$400 million.

3. Maximizing the volume of users access to the website, which is one of the most important goals of viral marketing; that is, increasing the number of individuals who will view the organization's website and thus convert them from users to customers depending on the nature and quality of the services used. Thus, customers help spread e-business organizations and their reach out. In addition, the number of advertisers who come to viral business organizations to place their banner ads on their websites is one of the most important success factors for these organizations that use viral marketing (Sandberg, 1999).

This was clearly demonstrated by the example of the Italian company, Sony, when they established an electronic channel open to all for communication and sending, which enabled the company to attract more than 130 thousand visitors in seven weeks only.

Viral marketing strategies

Viral marketing strategy, like all other strategies, is based

on an accurate information base on the target markets, in order to ensure the achievement of goals, and according to the nature of its work. Furthermore, the strategy of viral marketing is based on making use of customers in viral marketing operations voluntarily to spread messages to others to promote products, through social networks, or the word transmitted through e-mails.

According to the study of Thorson, (2006) and Phelps, et al, (2004) Saatchi, (2006), Porter and Golon, (2006), they classified these strategies into two categories:

Low Integration Strategies: this strategy is known also as the simplified strategy or the traditional method of marketing. It is about how to acquire and attract customers through the current customers. On this basis, the most important thing that this strategy aspires to in any organization is to make use of customers and motivate them to spread messages that serve marketing and promoting the products or services of this organization through expanding the base of Internet usage (Word of Mouse), where the current customers send the message to other people, and motivate them to forward it to others to and thus gaining new customers.

Examples of this are the free electronic services provided, and E-Greeting Cards services in viral marketing, as in the case of the Blue Mountain Art website, when a customer sends a greeting card to another party, the receiving party receives an email that states "Electronic greeting card waiting for you", and the recipient of the message visits the website by clicking on the attached link to view it (Abu Fara, 2008).

High Integration Strategies: This strategy is also called Active V-Marketing, which is one of the strategies used in viral marketing; this strategy is described as because it requires effective and high-level participation from customers in order to attract new customers. To illustrate this strategy more, we include some examples such as the case of Winamp.com, a site that provides digital songs service to customers to share with friends, as the website does not allow the use and listening to these songs unless the friends use the program Internet Magic Player provided by this website.

Another example is Amazon (Amazon.com) in the Amazon Participation Program where Amazon Company rewards every customer who attracts new customers to Amazon homepage, and the use of this strategy has been proven very effective.

Elements of a viral marketing strategy

Organizations have worked on adopting the viral marketing strategy adopted by Hotmail Company considering the success it achieved. This strategy was based on the following:

1. Giving value to products and services
2. Ease of transferring and spreading it to others
3. Spreading it from the smallest to the largest

4. Influencing the motives and behaviors of the subscribers;

5. Making use of all available means of communication and contact.

6. Making use of and appreciating all the benefits from the sources of others.

To facilitate the understanding of these elements, they need to be explained in a simpler way, as follows:

1) Giving added value to products and services to be passed on to others: The term free of charge is one of the terms that have a strong impact on people in terms of marketing terms, as most viral marketing programs give up the value of services until the attention of customers/clients is drawn through the term "free of charge"; the things included in it include e-mail services, free information, and free computer software. And this is evident through the second Wilson law of Internet marketing "the law of selling and giving" (cheap, inexpensive) which enables achieving future gains.

2) Ease of transferring it and spreading it to others: For example, what the doctor or nurse do when a person is infected with the influenza virus; it is the duty of the doctor and nurse towards other people to advise them to keep safety distance and avoid touching the infected person and wash their hands after shaking hands, because this virus is easily transmitted between people; accordingly, the advertising message must be simple, brief, convincing, effective and important to the recipient, and characterized by ease of transmission and repetition through e-mail, website, graphics, or software analysis.

3) Start spreading it easily from the smallest to the largest: The transmission and transfer of messages from one person to another, and through the Internet and social networks exactly as wildfire spreads, we see that when any organization places an advertisement on the network, the speed of its circulation and spread begins with the targets, and then moves through them to the groups to which they belong, and that the company's free e-mail service needs to have your mail, thus, transmission begins, and spread from the smallest to the largest takes place.

4) Making use of all available means for motivation and behavior: In order for any organization to advance its viral marketing plans, it must make use stimuli, including photos, videos, advertisements, material and moral rewards, or through perform any actions that stimulate and motivate communities, and their desires in order to become desirable, understandable, and more spread; and this is done through the Internet.

5) Making use of all available means of communication: This includes following up on the Internet, as social studies showed that one person communicates with (8-12) people, which helps in maintaining the current customers and gain new customers.

6) Making use of the advantages of other sources and benefiting from them: Viral plans and strategies use

different sources to upgrade, raise, and improve their reputation.

Organizations generally use electronic means of communication to apply viral marketing activities; these means include:

- 1) Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp....
- 2) YouTube
- 3) The company's website, mobile phones

CONCLUSION

Gleaned from the above aspects relating to viral marketing addressed in this study, it can be concluded that organizations need to pay more attention to the importance of viral marketing and viral campaigns, benefit from experiences in developed and the leading countries in the field of viral marketing, and benefit from the success they have achieved in the fields of e-business and e-commerce as a result of reducing cost, effort, and time. Also, organizations are recommended to continue with this policy, which is the viral marketing strategy, and activate this strategy to target maintaining the existing customers, attracting the largest possible number of new customers, motivating them, and making these customers become their promoting agents. And to achieve this aim, organizations in this regard should focus on a group of highly trusted and confident clients to rely on them to spread ideas, especially those who have extensive social relations with relatives and friends. Organizations and businesses are also recommended to use viral marketing tools in the field of viral campaigns and activate them continuously, and work to provide incentives to customers to attract them and make them revisit the organization's website. In addition to that, the study also stresses the need to activate and develop the policy of using electronic advertising messages, using appropriate and clear languages, raising the level of credibility, accuracy, and creativity, and work to be an important source of information and disseminate it. Finally, the word of mouth, whether it is from family, friends, or the work group, has an active role in encouraging the customer to choose the organization, which will consequently benefit the organization's reputation and fame, and thus maximizing its profits.

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